

E5.1 Design of Operational Components and Toolkit for Automated Discovery and SLA Assurance

v1.0

Publication Date: 30/09/2023

**DLT for 6G: Smart Marketplace
[6GENABLERS-DLT]
TSI-063000-2021-12**

**6G Networks Enabled through
Technology Driven Solutions
[6GENABLERS]**

**Programa de Universalización de
Infraestructuras Digitales para la Cohesión – 6G
I+D**

Work Package (WP)	P5
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Dissemination Level	PU
Type	RE

Dissemination Level	
PU	Public
PP	Restricted to other program participants
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium
CO	Confidential for consortium members only

Type	
PR	Prototype
RE	Report
SP	Specification
TO	Tool
OT	Other

Document version history				
Version	Author	Status	Date	Comments
v0.0	Adriana Fernández-Fernández	Template	28-08-23	Document structure, ToC
v0.1	Adriana Fernández-Fernández	Working Document	01-09-23	First round of contributions
v0.2	Adriana Fernández-Fernández	Version ready for tech review	14-09-23	Second round of contributions
v0.3	Adriana Fernández-Fernández	Version ready for QA review	21-09-23	Address tech review comments
v1.0	Adriana Fernández-Fernández	Version ready for submission	29-09-23	Address QA review comments

Table of Contents

List of Tables	4
List of Figures	5
List of Acronyms	6
Executive Summary	7
1 Introduction	8
1.1 Document Scope and Objectives	8
1.2 Relation to the Project's Activities	9
1.3 Structure of the Document	10
2 Smart Discovery System Specification	11
2.1 Overview	11
2.2 Design Guidelines	12
2.3 Sub-components	13
2.4 Interfaces and Data Models	14
2.5 Workflow Examples	17
3 Conclusion	20
4 References	21

List of Tables

Table 2-1 Smart Discovery interactions with other actors and systems	15
Table 2-2 Smart Discovery operations exposed via REST API endpoints	16

List of Figures

Figure 1-1 E5.1 positioning and relation to the project's activities	9
Figure 2-1 Smart Discovery internal architecture	13
Figure 2-2 Interplay of actors and systems with the Smart Discovery module	15
Figure 2-3 Smart Discovery operational pattern	17
Figure 2-4 Smart Discovery workflow example	18

List of Acronyms

6G	Sixth Generation
B5G	Beyond 5G
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
DLT	Distributed Ledger Technology
ID	Identifier
ML	Machine Learning
NLP	Natural Language Processing
NS	Network Service
OAS	OpenAPI Specification
RAN	Radio Access Network
REST	Representational State Transfer
SL	Supervised Learning
SLA	Service Level Agreement
UNICO	Universalización de Infraestructuras Digitales para la Cohesión
VNF	Virtual Network Function

Executive Summary

This document corresponds to the deliverable *E5.1 Design of Operational Components and Toolkit for Automated Discovery and SLA Assurance*, envisaged in the framework of the project 6GENABLERS-DLT (TSI-063000-2021-12). E5.1 marks the initial progress of Work Package 5 (P5), which centres on the pivotal aspects of Smart Discovery and SLA Assurance. P5 focuses on developing innovative methods to enhance the discovery and selection of offerings within the 6GENABLERS Marketplace, along with the ongoing monitoring and enforcement of SLA terms. The primary objective of P5 is to enrich the 6GENABLERS Marketplace with analytical tools that prioritize customization and flexibility, making it easier to identify available offers based on various criteria while facilitating real-time SLA updates. Within this context, this document is intended to fulfil the part of P5 related with the Automated Discovery by providing an extensive overview of the design framework and specifications for the operational components and toolkit required to automate resource and service discovery within the 6GENABLERS Marketplace. A similar document will be also generated for the part of SLA Assurance. The present document elucidates the technical intricacies, architectural considerations, and data models that form the foundation of this critical functionality. In essence, this deliverable offers a comprehensive blueprint for the implementation of Smart Discovery services within the 6GENABLERS Marketplace. It underscores the importance of automation and customization in meeting user requirements effectively, laying the groundwork for these crucial features.

1 Introduction

In the 6GENABLERS Marketplace, Smart Discovery is a fundamental service, which plays a crucial role in ensuring the efficient and reliable operation of the platform. Smart Discovery is responsible for matching consumer intents with available resources and services within the Marketplace.

To achieve this goal, Smart Discovery uses advanced algorithms, including Machine Learning (ML) techniques, to identify the most suitable offers that align with consumer needs. This includes considering various attributes such as location, technical specifications, pricing, and other relevant factors. It translates high-level consumer intents into specific resource and service requirements, helping consumers find the most appropriate offerings. This makes it easier for users to express their needs and preferences in a way that the system can understand. Smart Discovery exposes its capabilities via an intent-based interface, allowing other components of the Marketplace, such as the Smart Contract State Composer, to leverage its functionality. This enables seamless communication and collaboration among different parts of the platform.

In this context, this deliverable focuses on providing a comprehensive overview of the design framework and specifications for the operational components and toolkit essential to the automation of resource and service discovery within the 6GENABLERS Marketplace. This document elucidates the technical aspects, architectural considerations, and data models that underpin this critical functionality.

1.1 Document Scope and Objectives

This deliverable outlines the initial outcomes from Work Package 5 (P5), dedicated to unveiling the promising value of Automated Discovery and Service Level Agreement (SLA) Assurance, as core services of the 6GENABLERS Marketplace. As such, this document covers the part related to the Automated Discovery and provides the design of the operational components and toolkit envisioned for the Smart Discovery. In particular, this system is detailed in terms of design guidelines, internal architecture, interfaces, data models and workflow examples.

In correspondence with the aforementioned scope, the primary objectives of this document are as follows:

1. **Module Design Description:** The primary objective of this deliverable is to meticulously describe the design of operational modules providing Smart Discovery capabilities. It provides detailed insights into the structural and functional aspects of these modules, highlighting their roles and interactions within the broader platform.
2. **Service Mapping and Integration:** The document aims to map the provided services within the context of the overall Marketplace platform. It elucidates how these operational components seamlessly integrate with other components, ensuring cohesiveness and synergy.
3. **Interface and Data Model Specifications:** An essential objective is to provide precise specifications for interfaces and service endpoints associated with this system. This includes detailing the exposed operations, input and output formats and communication mechanisms to enable seamless interactions.

4. Operational Patterns: The deliverable outlines the sequence diagrams that drive the automation of resource discovery procedures. It specifies workflow examples for this system facilitating a clear understanding of the underlying operational patterns.

By achieving these objectives, this deliverable provides a robust framework and toolkit for Automated Discovery, laying the foundation for enhanced resource and service discovery within the 6GENABLERS Marketplace.

1.2 Relation to the Project's Activities

This deliverable presents the initial outcomes from Work Package 5 (P5), which covers the pillars related to Smart Discovery and SLA Assurance. This work package focuses on investigating and developing novel approaches to assist in the discovery and selection of Marketplace offers, accompanied by the monitoring and tracking of SLA terms fulfilment. The goal of this work package is to enrich the 6GENABLERS Marketplace with analytical tools that take customisation and flexibility as main guiding principles, to facilitate the identification of available offers, taking into account multiple criteria, and contribute to the monitoring and real-time updates of SLAs status.

Figure 1-1 E5.1 positioning and relation to the project's activities

As depicted in Figure 1-1, deliverable E5.1 is the joint result of the work done in the two tasks within P5, which are listed below:

- A5.1 – Dynamic Resource Discovery: This task focuses on the automated identification and selection of distributed resources from multiple administrative domains. In order to execute selection and ordering of offers for trading settlement, this task is meant to enrich the customer experience when interacting with the Marketplace via advanced and smart strategies to meet searching criteria.

- A5.2 – Proactive SLA Assurance: This task focuses on automating SLA signing underpinned by the Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT) capabilities. Moreover, it is meant to keep track of contract conditions and QoS measurements, ensuring violations are recorded on the ledger, as mechanisms for SLA assurance. Finally, this task will be interlinked to A5.1 in order to trigger the smart discovery of Marketplace offers as a means to avoid potential SLA violations.

Within this context, this document is intended to fulfil the part related to the task A5.1, focused on the Automated Discovery. A similar document will be also generated for the part of SLA Assurance corresponding to the work of task A5.2.

The work captured in this deliverable takes as input the system requirements defined within P2, and in particular by A2.4 (Smart Discovery System Requirements). At the same time, the modular design of the different components to be developed within P5 and provided in this document will feed the definition of the overall 6GENABLERS Marketplace architecture as part of A2.6 (DLT-anchored Smart Marketplace Architecture). Furthermore, this design will guide the subsequent development of prototypes to be carried out in P5, while ensuring the required interactions with other components associated to P3 and P4.

1.3 Structure of the Document

The current document is structured in several sections that detail the design specifications of the platform components defined to meet the goals of automated discovery. In particular, the document is structured as follows:

- Section 1: This section provides an overview of the document, including its objectives, the relationship to the project's activities, and the structure of the document itself.
- Section 2: This section presents the detailed specifications of the Smart Discovery system, providing the internal components architecture, interfaces, data models and workflow examples.
- Section 3: The conclusion section summarises the main findings and highlights the key takeaways from the document.
- Section 4: This section lists the sources and references cited throughout the document, providing a comprehensive list of the materials used to support the information presented.

2 Smart Discovery System Specification

In this section, we present the initial specifications of the components providing Automated Discovery capabilities. The objective is to furnish a detailed portrayal of the system, thereby facilitating precision in the specification and implementation tasks within P5. It is important to note that the components' specifications might be subject to subsequent enhancement and adjustment, as we progress in the implementation phase, which will be reflected in upcoming deliverables E5.2 and E5.3. Likewise, this work will directly contribute to the overall architecture definition to be initially provided in E2.2 and later refined in E2.3.

2.1 Overview

The core objective of the 6GENABLERS Marketplace is to facilitate collaborative interactions within dynamic B5G/6G environments, catering to instances where Operators and Service Providers necessitate the incorporation of third-party resources to better fulfil users demands, while addressing the sustainability expectation of next-generation systems. To achieve this, Asset Providers expose their resource offerings for sharing through the 6GENABLERS Marketplace. These resources span diverse segments of the network infrastructure, encompassing the Radio Access Network (RAN), edge, cloud, mobile core functions, and application functions, among others.

While directly exposing the catalogue of offers effectively serves as an interface for stakeholders, denoted as Asset Consumers, to interface with the Marketplace, certain limitations persist. Notably, this approach delegates the responsibility of optimal resource selection and nuanced exploration of available offers to the end customer. This often entails evaluating intricate trade-offs, wherein identifying the most suitable third-party resources is coupled with aligning these selections to specific scenarios or optimization criteria.

To provide a more refined solution, the introduction of the Smart Discovery application is of paramount importance. This innovative component seeks to enable programmatic and intent-driven offer discovery by leveraging advanced selection methodologies rooted in ML paradigms. By harnessing these techniques, the application aims to streamline the process of identifying and acquiring a tailored subset of offered network resources and services that precisely align with the consumer's requirements and expectations.

In pursuit of this objective, this module offers an Application Programming Interface (API) that provides intent-based assistance, harnessed in tandem with ML-based models to realize resource discovery of a highly intelligent nature. An intent-based API stands as an abstracted and simplified means for requesting an intent. In contrast to meticulously detailing the attributes of sought-after resource offerings (typically accomplished through elaborated filters), the API takes a declarative approach, prescribing the user intention. This prescription corresponds to a type of resource or service and an aspect to be prioritized, or more. In a nutshell, the module focuses on deciphering keywords within the provided intention and converting them into distinct groups or classes.

The foundation of this intelligent resource discovery is underpinned by supporting ML-based models. Central to this approach, is the utilization of data clustering methodologies, which pool resources together, based on the identification of common

features. In this way, real-time predictions are performed to group incoming offers regarding its affiliation with one of the established clusters.

2.2 Design Guidelines

The Smart Discovery component serves as a cornerstone in enabling intelligent offer discovery and efficient interactions within dynamic and highly populated Marketplace environments. To ensure the seamless functioning and effective realization of its objectives, a set of comprehensive design guidelines has been formulated.

These guidelines are strategically crafted to facilitate the development and deployment of the component in a manner that aligns with both technical excellence and user-centric functionality. Let's delve into these guidelines to shed light on the best practices that underpin the successful implementation of the Smart Discovery component.

- **Modular Architecture:** Develop the Smart Discovery component as a modular architecture to ensure scalability and maintainability. This facilitates the addition of new functionalities or updates without disrupting the entire system.
- **Separation of Concerns:** Divide the component into well-defined functional entities, each responsible for a specific task (such as offline clustering, online classification, and intent-based discovery, which will be further elaborated in Section 2.3). This approach enhances clarity, ease of troubleshooting, and independent development.
- **API-driven Structure:** Implement an API-driven structure that allows seamless interactions between the Smart Discovery component and other modules of the Marketplace framework. Clearly define the input and output formats for each API to ensure smooth integration.
- **ML Model Flexibility:** Build the ML-based clustering and classification models with modularity in mind. This allows for swapping out models as advancements in ML occur, ensuring adaptability to changing requirements.
- **Real-time Processing:** Implement online mechanisms for real-time processing of incoming offers and discovery requests. Consider the periodic update of models training based on new offers to preserve accuracy over time.
- **Natural Language Processing (NLP):** Implement NLP techniques for the processing of incoming discovery intents. Integrate libraries or frameworks for language processing, ensuring the accurate translation of user intents to available offers.
- **Configurability:** Provide configuration options for setting parameters like algorithms, model training intervals, among others. This allows system administrators to customize the component to suit specific needs.

By adhering to these guidelines, the Smart Discovery component can embody a robust architecture, scalable capabilities, and advanced functionalities, providing a seamless experience for users while accommodating the intricacies of Artificial Intelligence (AI)-powered systems. Following these design guidelines ensures that the Smart Discovery component is not only technically robust but also aligned with the evolving needs of the users and the system's objectives.

2.3 Sub-components

The Smart Discovery component serves the primary purpose of furnishing the Marketplace with advanced functionalities designed to enable the intelligent identification of available offers. Specifically, this module facilitates the automated recognition and curation of multi-party resources within the Marketplace that encompasses diverse network resource and service types. At its core, the Smart Discovery component is geared towards two pivotal objectives: the intelligent establishment of relationships within offers and the translation of users' high-level discovery intents. To realize these ambitions, the component harnesses the power of ML-based models, utilizing them to execute a sophisticated discovery process encompassing resource and service offers prominently featured within the Marketplace.

The internal architecture of the Smart Discovery component, depicted in Figure 2-1, comprises three subcomponents following the design guidelines of modularity and separation of concerns. These subcomponents collectively rely on a suite of databases, serving as repositories for data exchange and storage. This repository encompasses essential information concerning for instance the ML models, clusters features, and standard deviation. Notably, these stored clusters features, and standard deviation are subsequently leveraged by the intent-based subcomponent to effectively map users' requests to classified offers.

Figure 2-1 Smart Discovery internal architecture

As illustrated in Figure 2-1, the Smart Discovery component internally comprises the following functional entities, each contributing to its overall operation:

- **Offline Clustering Function:** This entity harnesses advanced clustering techniques to unveil patterns among offers within a specific category. The procedure involves training a clustering model offline, which learns the underlying similarities within the attributes for each offer type. By doing so, artificial clusters are generated. To uphold the model's accuracy over time, this process can be periodically repeated (e.g., after receiving a designated set of offers or during system maintenance). Thus, the training dataset includes incoming offers accumulated since the previous training session.
- **Online Classification Function:** Leveraging Supervised Learning (SL) principles, this entity capitalizes on the clusters generated from the previous step,

13

using them as labelled data for training. During runtime, the trained model is capable of classifying each incoming offer into its corresponding cluster. The cluster assignment is subsequently integrated into the offer information stored in the ledger. Moreover, the model can be retrained whenever updates to the offer clusters are introduced.

- **Intent-based Discovery Function:** This critical component receives retrieval requests for offers in the form of high-level intentions, articulated in natural language. It automatically translates these intents into a curated array of matching available offers. The intentions encapsulate users' needs and preferences, aligned with the offer type (e.g., edge, RAN) and prioritized characteristics (e.g., memory capacity, operating band). Specifically, this function translates received intentions into specific clusters, thereby retrieving the most suitable offers. Integrating sophisticated NLP techniques, it dynamically translates intentions into a selection of offers, precisely tailored to meet users' requirements.

These mechanisms collaborate within the Smart Discovery component, collectively culminating in an intelligent and dynamic system that adeptly identifies patterns, categorizes offers. Thus, ensuring the accuracy and relevance of cluster assignments, and comprehends and acts upon user intentions, facilitating a streamlined and responsive interaction between users and the 6GENABLERS Marketplace.

These submodules effectively fulfil the capabilities and functional prerequisites outlined in deliverable E2.1 [1]. With provisions for an AI-driven model catering to offline clustering and online prediction, coupled with the intent-based discovery, the system boasts the ability to intelligently categorize and autonomously unearth network resource and service offerings according to various parameters.

2.4 Interfaces and Data Models

In terms of interfaces, the Smart Discovery is expected to interact with a range of key components and actors. Foremost, its discovery service is to be consumed by the Marketplace stakeholders looking to discover the most convenient offers (i.e., asset consumers). Likewise, the capacity to re-compute the clusters used to group the offers will be exposed so the Admin of each Marketplace instance can trigger this operation.

Within the Marketplace framework, the Marketplace DLT and the Smart Contract are the systems that will actively engage with the Smart Discovery module to leverage its functionality. In particular, the Offering API as part of the DLT system shares incoming offers with the Smart Discovery module for their online classification. In turn, the Smart Discovery component remains engaged with the Offering API in order to extend the offer information with the resulting cluster, ensuring all the relevant information is always committed to the ledger. Additionally, the Smart Contract State Composer from the Smart Contract system harnesses the discovery capability of the Smart Discovery module. In particular, it relegates to the Smart Discovery component the user request looking for the most compatible offers in order to disclose tailored resources that satisfy the user intent.

Table 2-1 summarizes the interactions of the Smart Discovery module with other actors and systems. The involved Representational State Transfer (REST) interfaces are based on OpenAPI specification (OAS).

Table 2-1 Smart Discovery interactions with other actors and systems

ID	Description	Type	Direction
I-Ext-SD	The Admin of every Marketplace Instance consumes the clustering endpoint.	OAS REST API	Input
I-DLT-SD	DLT system consumes the classification endpoint. Smart Discovery consumes the offer retrieval endpoint of the DLT system.	OAS REST API	Bi-directional
I-SC-SD	Assets Consumer through the Smart Contract system consumes the discovery endpoint.	OAS REST API	Input

For the sake of visualization, this interplay of actors and Marketplace systems with the Smart Discovery module is also depicted in Figure 2-2.

Figure 2-2 Interplay of actors and systems with the Smart Discovery module

To perform the aforementioned functionalities, the interfaces exposed by the Smart Discovery component integrate three main operations, which are described below in Table 2-2. They represent the operations that the Smart Discovery component makes available through its OAS REST APIs, to be consumed by the actors and additional components from the Marketplace DLT and Smart Contract systems, that exploit the Smart Discovery as depicted in Figure 2-2. Specifications for the endpoints at the Marketplace DLT system for retrieving the offers stored in the ledger are provided in the DLT system design deliverable (E3.1) [2].

Table 2-2 Smart Discovery operations exposed via REST API endpoints

Operation name: Clustering		
Description	Endpoint for triggering the clusters re-computation. This process integrates the training of the algorithms used for the clustering and classification functions, taking as the training dataset incoming offers accumulated since the last performed training.	
Input Parameters	Type	Description
Model	String	The model indicates the ML model subject to training. Valid values are expected to include the unsupervised learning models implemented for the clustering, as well as the supervised learning model implemented for the classification.
Offer Category	String	The offer category for which the clusters need to be computed. Valid values correspond to the categories supported in the Marketplace (e.g., edge, cloud, RAN, VNF, and NS).
Output Parameters	Type	Description
-	-	-
Notes		
This operation is expected to be performed to uphold the model's accuracy over time (e.g., considering some periodic intervals, reaching a given number of new offers, among others).		

Operation name: Classification		
Description	Endpoint for classifying an offer, resulting in the determination of a cluster ID. This operation will extend the offer information to be stored in the ledger, by adding to it the determined Cluster ID.	
Input Parameters	Type	Description
Product Offer	Object	Object containing the product offer information based on the TM Forum Product Offering Data Model [3].
Output Parameters	Type	Description
Cluster ID	Integer	Numeric identifier of the cluster which the processed offer is associated to, based on their similar features.
Notes		

Operation name: Discovery		
Description	Endpoint for discovering available offers, returning a list of most suitable offers for final selection.	
Input Parameters	Type	Description
Discovery Intent	String	String containing the intent for desired offers. The intent must include the offer category and the required features to be met. This parameter will be translated into the specific cluster(s) of offers that correspond with the requested attributes.
Output Parameters	Type	Description
List of Offers	List	A list of offers matching the supplied discovery intent. Offers could be ranked based on some default criteria, or according to some criteria included in the intent.
Notes		

2.5 Workflow Examples

The operational pattern of the Smart Discovery component encompasses a dynamic sequence of interactions and processes that collectively drive its intelligent resource discovery mechanism, which are depicted in Figure 2-3.

Figure 2-3 Smart Discovery operational pattern

The Offline Clustering function, in an offline learning phase, meticulously groups network offers into clusters based on common attributes, optimizing the discovery process. After the initial bootstrapping of the system, for which a default training dataset is embedded into the component, this operation can be repeated periodically using then the offers that have been received over such given period as the training dataset.

As the system receives new offers, the Online Classification function employs the trained ML model to predict the cluster affiliation of incoming offers in real time. The predicted cluster is then relayed to the Marketplace DLT for adding it to the offer information to be recorded in the ledger.

Once intent-based requests are received, the Intent-based Discovery function deciphers the intent and translates it into the corresponding cluster(s) that best reflect the customer expectations. These insights are then used to retrieve the existing offers within the specified clusters from the Marketplace DLT. This dynamic mechanism enables seamless interaction between the Smart Discovery component and Marketplace stakeholders, culminating in efficient, tailored resource discovery that aligns precisely with users' requirements and preferences.

In a more detailed way, the operational workflow underpinning the Smart Discovery services is visually depicted in Figure 2-4. This illustrative scenario features two key players in the Marketplace realm: the Asset Provider and the Asset Consumer. Broadly, the workflow entails the three primary processes: 1) the classification of a new incoming offer, 2) the translation of user intents for the subsequent retrieval of relevant offers, and 3) the re-computation of clusters. The three processes are portrayed sequentially for the sake of clarity, and under the reasoning of populating first the Marketplace, getting discovery requests afterwards, and conducting the models' re-training at a much later stage in time. However, it is important to indicate that once the component is operational, these phases are independent from each other, and they can be performed without

having to follow the exact same sequence as illustrated in the workflow example. For instance, the discovery request can arrive at any point in time, and the response will be aligned with the resources and services available in the Marketplace that best satisfy the submitted intent. These stages are further elaborated next.

Figure 2-4 Smart Discovery workflow example

➤ **Classification:** Upon new offer submission, this offer information is fed from the Smart Contract State Composer to the Offering API, which in turn contacts the Smart Discovery. There, an online SL model (served by the Online Classification functional entity) springs into action, effectively determining the relevant group (cluster) to which the offer belongs. The identifier of the resulting cluster is communicated back to the Offering API. The resulting classified offer—now enriched with its identified cluster affiliation—is subsequently disseminated across domains via the DLT network. Importantly, once an offer is recorded on the DLT, it becomes universally accessible for discovery and purchase by all trading entities.

➤ **Discovery:** In this phase, the consumer through the Smart Contract State Composer articulates an intent for discovering an offer. The provided discovery information, channelled via the intent-based interface (within the Intent-based Discovery functional entity), undergoes automated translation to identify the requested features and mapping into the cluster(s) that best capture the consumer's expectations articulated in the intent. The resulting cluster(s) is then used to retrieve the corresponding offers from the DLT through the Offering API, which are then subsequently returned. This subset of offers can be further scrutinized in the consumer domain to select the most fitting offer.

➤ Clustering: Initially, a default training dataset comprising a variety of values for the features of several offer types, and stored in the Smart Discovery's data base, is used for setting the clusters the first time, which are then used to build the classification ML model that works online to label new offers. At running time, the re-computation of clusters can be manually triggered (using the Offline Clustering interface) by each stakeholder owning a Marketplace instance. This operation integrates the re-training of every ML model for each one of the supported offer categories. In this case, the training dataset is formed by getting the latest offers that have been stored in the DLT since the last training.

3 Conclusion

The document outlines the design framework and specifications for operational components and a toolkit that are crucial for automating resource and service discovery within the 6GENABLERS Marketplace. It delves into technical aspects, architectural considerations, data models, and workflow examples, presenting a comprehensive view of this essential functionality.

The document underscores the design principles of customization and flexibility, catering to the diverse needs of the Marketplace stakeholders. It explores how the toolkit and operational components can be adapted to accommodate various scenarios. This ensures that the deliverable addresses the specified acceptance criteria and contributes to the overarching objectives of the project.

In terms of enhanced resource and service discovery, the deliverable describes the specifications and operation of the Smart Discovery system within the Marketplace, leveraging smart techniques and predictive analytics to provide users with the most relevant and suitable offers based on parameterizable searching criteria.

The Smart Discovery system contributes to the seamless and data-driven operation of the 6GENABLERS Marketplace by helping users find the right resources and services. Together with other systems, this component enhances the overall functionality and reliability of the Marketplace, making it a valuable platform for resource and service trading in the 6G ecosystem.

In summary, this deliverable serves as a foundation for Smart Discovery services within the 6GENABLERS Marketplace, emphasizing the automation and customization required to meet user needs effectively.

4 References

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